

ABSTRACT

This descriptive research study aimed to determine the research competence of 256 Faculty of State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) in Iloilo. Specifically, this study was conducted to determine the level of research competence of Faculty in SUCs in terms of Basic Skills, Problem-Solving, and Critical Thinking Skills; Dissemination of Research Results; Function of Faculty Researchers in SUCs; and Other Relevant Key Competencies; to determine the significant difference in the level of research competence of Faculty in SUCs when grouped according to the level of education, and Faculty rank. The data was collected using a researcher-made questionnaire. Results showed that, as a whole, Faculty in SUCs were "Competent" in all categories. When grouped according to the level of education, Master's Degree, and Doctorate Degree/Level, teachers assessed themselves as "Competent ."When grouped according to Faculty Rank, all Faculty, regardless of Faculty Rank, are "Competent ."No significant difference existed in the level of research competence of Faculty when grouped according to the level of education. When grouped according to Faculty Rank, no significant difference existed in the level of research competence in terms of Basic Skills and Other Relevant Key Competencies. Significant differences existed in the level of research competence in terms of Problem-solving, Critical Thinking Skills, Dissemination of Research Results, and Function of Faculty Researchers in SUCs. Faculty Rank is not a significant factor in determining the research competence of Faculty in SUCs in terms of Basic Skills and Other Relevant Key Competencies, but significant in terms of Problem-Solving and Critical Thinking Skills, Dissemination of Research Results, and Faculty Researcher Function in SUCs.

Keywords: *Research Competence, Faculty Researchers, State Colleges and Universities*

INTRODUCTION

Globalization has touched many aspects of our life, including education. The more developed the country is, the greater its emphasis on education and its role in economic and social development. Research plays a significant role in our existence as a society. It is in its findings that the modern world is now enjoying the advances in science and technology.

In higher education institutions, research is one of the essential functions, along with instruction and community extension (CHED, 2009). Research in higher education across disciplines ensures the continued growth and development of the entire higher education sector. Research is a criterion for success in higher education institutions worldwide because it entails transferring teaching skills and research output. State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) are governed by the policies and mandates of the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), which are geared mainly towards improving research productivity. This is accomplished through the National Higher Education Research Agenda (NHERA), which embodies program thrusts to foster genuine research culture in higher education. Several accrediting bodies consider research one of the most important characteristics to evaluate during the accreditation process. The Association of Accredited Chartered Colleges and Universities in the Philippines (AACCUP) emphasized the importance of research in its accreditation instrument, which is identical to the AACCUP's program accreditation.

Research output is an essential aspect of assessment for academic positions. It remains the responsibility of the institution to encourage researchers with grants and collaboration with other researchers across disciplines (Galleto, 2016). In academic institutions, the academic reputation of professors lies in their ability to investigate scientifically and to come up with new ideas, knowledge, and discoveries that will improve existing practices, processes, and strategies (Gomez & Panaligan, 2013). Research is also one of the accreditation standards in assessing the development of competent professionals. Likewise, in evaluating programs and institutions relative to accreditation, the research element is one of the areas being assessed by the accreditors. This concretizes the ability of the university to produce research that would generate knowledge for the productivity of the institutions.

Despite CHED, AACCUP, and other accrediting bodies' initiatives and parameters, there still needs to be a more substantial research culture in education due to a lack of research skills and knowledge training for instructors and poor and inadequate research in higher education. Some research proposals are simply that: proposals. They are never carried out. Some of the research findings are presented at scientific conferences. However, they are not published in peer-reviewed journals or

used for development, institutional change, innovation, or commercialization.

There are many ways to acquire research competencies. Knowledge alone is unlikely to allow an individual to achieve competency. Other experiences that complement training should reinforce the acquisition of competencies. The importance of research capability among the teaching personnel should be kept from the backseat because the backbone of development in a university is found in the research competence of all teachers, novice and experienced ones (Pamatmat, 2016).

When research is put into writing and subsequently published, it contributes to the expansion of knowledge based on scientific inquiry and investigation, which aims at the discovery of facts and theories of laws (Bueno, 2017; 2019; Bueno, 2019a; 2019b; Basilio & Bueno, 2019). In 2018, the Philippines produced 2,237 scientific and technical journal articles (World Bank, 2021). This number is less than 4,286 in Vietnam, 11,459 in Singapore, 12,514 in Thailand, 23,661 in Malaysia, 26,948 in Indonesia, 422,808 in the USA, and 528,263 in China. Looking at these numbers, the Philippines needs to speed up its effort to increase research competence to keep at par with its neighboring countries regarding research.

Faculty members have an essential role in the publication of scientific papers. Their competence in carrying out research activities helps determine academic research output. This study investigated the research competence of State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) faculty members.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This is a descriptive research study wherein the quantitative approach was used to determine the research competence of the Faculty of State Universities and Colleges in the Province of Iloilo. For this study, a qualitative survey supported the collected quantitative data.

Respondents. This is a descriptive research study wherein the quantitative approach was used to determine the research competence of the Faculty of State Universities and Colleges in the Province of Iloilo. For this study, a qualitative survey supported the collected quantitative data.

Data Collection Procedure. Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the Campus Administrators of the 4 SUCs in the Province of Iloilo. Once permission was obtained, the data-gathering instrument was either sent via electronic mail or personally distributed and administered by the researchers to the respondents. In some cases where the respondents were not available for personal administration of the instrument, the researcher asked the help of the office staff to administer the questionnaire to the respondents. The data was collected during the second visit. The data was collected through Google Forms for the electronic administration of the instrument. Telephone and social media chat/interviews were conducted to support the collected quantitative data. The data collection was conducted for six (6) months, from July – to December 2021.

Data Analysis Procedure. Upon retrieval, the data gathered were encoded, tallied, interpreted, and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21. This study utilized both descriptive and inferential analyses. Mean, and standard deviation was the statistical tool used for descriptive analysis. T-test, One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were the statistical tools used in the inferential data analysis. In the descriptive analysis, mean, and standard deviation were used. The mean determined the levels of research competence, whereas the standard deviation determined the homogeneity of the responses. Moreover, t-test and ANOVA were used to determine the differences in the level of research competence of the Faculty of SUCs. The .05 alpha significance level was used as a criterion for accepting or rejecting the null hypotheses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Research Competence of Faculty in SUCs When Taken as a Whole

The level of research competence of Faculty in SUCs, when taken as a whole, is presented in Table 1. Results show that the Faculty in SUCs are "Competent" in all categories ($M = 3.89$, $sd = 0.61$).

The Faculty is "Competent" in terms of Basic Skills ($M = 4.01$, $sd = 0.62$). This result implies that Faculty in SUCs have a good level of knowledge in the use of libraries and information technologies; they have little difficulty in finding and using resources, and they have an appropriate level of time management skills. They also have a good understanding of the difference between primary and secondary resources. The results conform with several studies as follows: Roman (2021) reported that competencies about problems and backgrounds, literature, sources and citations, theories and frameworks, research methods, research instrumentations, sampling techniques, research ethics,

data analysis procedures, and making interpretation, conclusion, recommendation, and implication are all in the low extent category, while the competency of the HEI faculty in research types is on the average level. Faculty were well-versed in research capability knowledge and technical components (Narang et al., 2016). Bueno (2017) also reported that Faculty members still need to improve their mastery of research skills, evidenced by their outputs, and aid graduate students in improving their research abilities and professional progress through further research activities. Teachers have average skills in accessing, using, and evaluating information and understanding various sources and where to obtain them (Basilio & Bueno, 2019). Also, Tahsildar & Hasani R. (2021) studied the inventory of research skills and indicated that Faculty perceived to have mid-level research skills with low-level research productivity as evidenced by their research production. Furthermore, teachers have a reasonable level of competence in conducting research, designing and experimental studies, selecting and developing research instruments, selecting appropriate statistical tools (Alumbro et al., 2015), and preparing a manuscript for publication (Basilio et al., 2019).

Regarding problem-solving and critical thinking skills, Faculty regard themselves as "Competent" ($M = 3.91$, $sd = 0.62$). This means that Faculty have average skills in those competencies mentioned above. The results are consistent with the findings of Rodriguez et al. (2021), where, on average; the Faculty's research competency is that of a practitioner in research conceptualization, research design, data collection, data processing and analysis, and research application. Faculty members have average knowledge of applying research findings and are capable and eager to do so, but they need more speed and flexibility of a proficient researcher.

In a study conducted by Dinagsao (2013), more than one-third of their faculty respondents have below essential competencies, while the rest need more confidence that they have beyond basic skills in management, communication, and data analysis in research. There are also studies that show that Faculty were well-versed in the knowledge and technical components of research capability (Narang et al., 2016), competent to do research (Tan, 2012), and have a high level of research capability (Enero et al., 2017) and competence in various research activities (Cuntapay et al., 2014). Pardo et al. (2018) also found that Faculty researchers are "Very capable" of identifying and handling correct data and following proper theses/dissertation writing mechanics.

Regarding the Dissemination of Research Results, results in Table 2 show that the Faculty in SUCs are "Competent" ($M = 3.84$, $sd = 0.68$). This means that the Faculty in SUCs have a good level of competence in verbal or written expression of ideas, identifying relevant journals for publication of research output, capability in preparing research reports for publication, presentation of research results in front of an audience, and translation of research output for the benefit of stakeholders/ beneficiaries. The results align with Gomez and Panaligan's (2013) findings, which reported that the faculty respondents were highly competent in the research format but needed reinforcement in developing their communication skills. Bueno (2017) also reported that Faculty were satisfactory in exhibiting mastery of research skills regarding research activities and publications. Teachers reported an acceptable level of competence in preparing manuscripts for publication (Basilio et al., 2019).

Regarding the Function of Faculty Researchers in SUCs, the Faculty is "Competent" ($M = 3.80$, $sd = 0.71$). This means that Faculty have a good level of participation in activities that contribute to the development of a body of knowledge relevant to higher education; the capability to plan and execute research studies that address current and significant issues; the capability to submit research grants proposals to major funding agencies, assistance and support to other researchers, and contribution of research findings in the advancement of theories in a specific field of study. The results contradict the findings of Gomez and Panaligan (2013), which reported that Faculty respondents seem to need competency in research design development and constructing questionnaires. Teachers reported fair competence in research (Cuadra et al., 2015), organizing an experimental study, and selecting and constructing research instruments. Empirical evidence revealed that teacher-researchers are skilled in both conceptual skills (De la Cruz, 2016) and technical research areas (Abarquez et al., 2013). According to Roman (2021), the research competencies of the HEI faculty based on the research competency test generally reveals a low extent (32.56%). In particular, competencies in theories and frameworks, research methods, research instrumentations, sampling techniques, research ethics, data analysis procedures, and making interpretation, conclusion, recommendations, and implications are all in the low extent category, while the competency of the HEI faculty in research types is on the average level.

Regarding Other Relevant Key Competencies of Faculty in SUCs, results show that Faculty of SUCs are "Competent" ($M = 3.85$, $sd = 0.68$). This means that Faculty have an excellent competency in conducting electronic literature searches using the internet and library databases and using impact factors and citation indices to describe the paper's quality. Faculty members can write a study proposal that includes the main objectives, introduction, hypotheses, design, statistical analysis, power

calculation, ethical considerations, and dissemination; and apply it to a local research ethics committee for ethical approval. This result agrees with the findings of (Cuadra et al., 2015), wherein teachers reported an appropriate level of competence in selecting and constructing research instruments and choosing relevant statistical tools. The current findings do not conform with that of Roman (2021), which revealed that the research competencies of the HEI faculty are all in the low extent category in terms of competencies in research methods, research instrumentations, sampling techniques, research ethics, data analysis procedures, and making interpretation, conclusion, recommendation, and implication. The result also reflects that competency in research ethics is at the bottom among the ten parameters. This result about the research competencies of the respondents, as reflected on the research competency test, shows that there is a need to upgrade the competency level in research in all aspects. On the other hand, the results contradict that of Pardo et al. (2018), which revealed that, in terms of conceptual, computational, and technical skills, the Faculty has "Very High" research capabilities, which means that the Faculty is very much capable of identifying research and instructional problems and in transforming them into research problems, analyzing and interpreting study outcomes, formulating specific findings, and drawing conclusions and recommendations.

When the total mean per group was assessed, Basic Skills got the highest mean ($M = 4.01$, $sd = 0.62$), while the Function of Faculty Researcher in SUCs, got the lowest mean ($M = 3.80$, $sd = 0.71$) but still interpreted as "Competent." This can be explained by the fact that faculty entry is at the Master's level, and they have already completed writing or have undergone research studies during their baccalaureate and Master's studies; thus, they already have basic research abilities. The results agree with Rodriguez et al. (2021), who found that Faculty chose a Master's course in research as their source of research competency. Undergraduate courses in research, seminars and training, actual research experience, reference materials on research by study, a doctoral course in research, field exposure/trip, or study missions are also a source of research competency.

The above findings were validated in interviews conducted with the Faculty respondents. From the interview, respondents revealed that they still need to learn how to do research. *Personal characteristics such as knowledge/ intelligence, commitment, and written communications skills affect research performance. Knowledge/Intelligence indeed affects the quality of the research output - a person's education level better equips this.*

As one respondent mentioned, *a full-fledged Ph.D. degree researcher is often better than a college researcher. As a researcher, one is presumed to have mastered written communication skills. These are all crucial in research. Lousy written constructs could impose unprofessionalism and light outputs not suited for publication. Basic knowledge and updates on new methods, theories/ concepts, instruments, and available technology (for example, Turnitin and Mendeley) are essential for conducting research and improving research performance.* They also stated that collaboration with other institutions to establish a connection is one factor in faculty research performance in SUCs. Time management is one of the basic skills in doing research. Faculty respondents also pointed out that they need more time management skills. They have yet to establish a timeline for when to finish the research. This result conforms with the study of Chan (2021), which reported that only half of the faculty respondents could complete their research project/study.

Table 1. Mean Results on the Level of Research Competence of Faculty in SUCs When Taken as a Whole

Category	n	Mean	sd	Description
As a whole	256	3.89	0.61	Competent
Basic Skills	256	4.01	0.62	Competent
Problem-solving and Critical Thinking Skills	256	3.91	0.70	Competent
Dissemination of Research Results	256	3.84	0.68	Competent
The function of Faculty Researchers in SUCs	256	3.80	0.71	Competent
Other Relevant Key Competencies	256	3.85	0.68	Competent

Note: 4.21–5.00 Highly Competent; 3.41–4.20 Competent; 2.61–3.40 Moderately Competent; 1.81–2.60 Less Competent; 1.00–1.80 Not Competent

Level of Research Competence of Faculty in SUCs When Grouped According to Level of Education

Table 2 reveals that Master's Degree and Doctorate Degree/Level teachers assessed themselves as "Competent" ($M = 3.90$, $sd = 0.55$, $M = 3.87$, $sd = 0.64$, respectively). This means that the Faculty is "Competent" in all categories regardless of the level of education. This can be explained by the fact that faculty admission is at the Master's level, and they have already done writing or research studies during their baccalaureate and Master's degrees. Undergraduate and graduate curricula

offer a variety of methods for determining whether or not a student has met the required competency for a course, class, or degree (Jamieson & Saunders, 2020). Faculty members' research skills are often developed through mentoring during their initial job and are primarily obtained through schooling (Byrne & Keefe, 2002). During their Master's and undergraduate research courses, Faculty strengthen their research skills (Rodriguez, 2021). Competence develops a new mental formation while mastering certain activities during the research learning process (Prosekov et al., 2020).

Regarding Basic Skills, they were found to be "Competent" ($M = 3.99$, $sd = 0.59$; $M = 4.02$, $sd = 0.63$ for Master's Degree and Doctorate Degree/Level, respectively). This is probably because faculty admission is at the Master's level. They have done writing or research studies during their baccalaureate and Master's degrees, indicating they have basic research skills. After all, undergraduate and graduate curricula provide many ways to evaluate whether someone attains the required standards within a course, class, or degree (Jamieson & Saunders, 2020). Research competency of Faculty members' research skills are mainly acquired through schooling and are typically developed through mentoring during their first job (Byrne & Keefe, 2002). Faculty develop their research skills during their Master's and undergraduate research courses. This result can be ascribed to more respondents having a Master's degree (Rodriguez, 2021). The development of research competency is the final result of education. As a new mental formation, competence develops while mastering certain activities during the research learning process (Prosekov et al., 2020).

Regarding problem-solving and critical thinking skills, both the Master's Degree holder and Doctorate Degree/Level Faculty were "Competent" ($M = 3.95$, $sd = 0.64$; $M = 3.89$, $sd = 0.76$, respectively). Faculty in SUCs, as previously said, have at least a Master's degree, providing them with a suitable environment for problem-solving and critical thinking. The findings align with those of Rodriguez et al. (2021), who found that the Faculty's research competency in research conceptualization, research design, data collecting, data processing and analysis, and research application is at par with that of a practitioner. According to Dinagsao (2013), more than a third of their faculty respondents have fundamental competencies in management, communication, and data analysis in research. The remainder is still determining if they have skills beyond basic. Furthermore, the Faculty was well-versed in the knowledge and technical components of research capability (Narag et al., 2016), competent to do research (Tan, 2012), and possessed a high level of research capability (Enero et al., 2017; Cuntapay et al., 2014).

Concerning dissemination of research results, Master's Degree holder and Doctorate Degree/Level Faculty were "Competent" ($M = 3.87$, $sd = 0.62$; $M = 3.82$, $sd = 0.73$, respectively). This demonstrates that the professors have an excellent ability to communicate their thoughts. They have a good level of confidence in finding a relevant journal for their research work. Teachers can prepare research reports for publication and present them confidently in front of an audience. They can also translate their study findings to benefit stakeholders and beneficiaries. The findings back up Gomez and Panaligan's (2013) findings that faculty respondents were highly competent in the research format but needed to improve their communication skills. Bueno (2017) also reported that Faculty were only satisfactory in demonstrating mastery of research skills about research output. The results of Basilio et al. (2019) revealed that teachers have a reasonable level of competence in writing papers for publication.

The Faculty is also "Competent" regarding the Function of Faculty Researchers in SUCs with $M = 3.81$, $sd = 0.73$, and $M = 3.80$, $sd = 0.68$ for Doctorate Degree/Level and Master's Degree holders, respectively. This indicates that professors are sufficiently involved in creating a knowledge body relevant to higher education. They can organize and carry out research investigations that address current and pressing topics and submit proposals to major funding agencies. The teachers are constructive and supportive of other scholars—teachers' research discoveries aid in advancing theory in a specific field of study.

For other relevant key competencies, Master's Degree holder and Doctorate Degree/Level Faculty were "Competent" ($M = 3.91$, $sd = 0.62$; $M = 3.81$, $sd = 0.72$, respectively). This indicates that regardless of education level, teachers can use the internet and library databases to conduct electronic literature searches and use the impact factors and citation indices to describe the paper's quality. They have good skills in using and interpreting fundamental statistical analysis, such as tests for normality and proper usage of parametric and non-parametric statistics tests. The findings are inconsistent with those of Gomez and Panaligan (2013), who found that faculty respondents require proficiency in study design formulation and questionnaire construction. Teachers indicated decent expertise in doing research (Cuadra et al., 2015), planning an experimental study, and selecting and building research tools. According to empirical evidence, teacher researchers are talented in conceptual (De la Cruz, 2016) and technical areas of study (Abarquez et al., 2013).

When the total mean group was assessed, for both Master's Degree holders and Doctorate Degree/Level, Basic Skills got the highest mean ($M = 3.99$, $sd = 0.59$; $M = 4.02$, $sd = .63$, respectively), while Function of Faculty Researchers in SUCs got the lowest mean ($M = 3.87$, $sd = 0.62$; $M = 3.81$, $sd = 0.62$). The findings are consistent with the findings of Rodriguez et al. (2021), who found out that, on average, the Faculty's research competency is that of a practitioner in the areas of research conceptualization, research design, data collection, data processing, and analysis, and research application. Faculty members have average knowledge and are capable and eager to put it to use, but they need more speed and flexibility of a proficient researcher. Likewise, Bueno (2017) found out that Faculty still need to improve their mastery of research skills as shown by their outputs, provision of assistance to graduate students in developing competencies in research, and professional growth through further research endeavors. Furthermore, Master Teachers (those who have earned MA/MS units) have average skills in searching, using, and evaluating information, as well as understanding various sources of information and where to get them (Bueno & Basilio, 2019). They have a good understanding of experimental study design, selecting and building research instruments, selecting relevant statistical tools, and preparing manuscripts for publication. However, they still need to enhance their research skills. These individuals also require support in developing their research skills. Similarly, Chan (2021) pointed out that most Ph.D. holders were doing well in research because of aiming for a professorial item from research involvement. Educators with a Ph.D. degree are expected to be more research-skilled and productive than those with Master's degrees only.

Table 2. Mean Results on the Level of Research Competence of Faculty in SUCs When Grouped According to Level of Education

Category	Master's Degree				Doctorate Degree/Level			
	n	Mean	sd	Description	n	Mean	sd	Description
As a whole	105	3.90	0.55	Competent	151	3.87	0.64	Competent
Basic Skills	105	3.99	0.59	Competent	151	4.02	0.63	Competent
Problem-solving and Critical Thinking Skills	105	3.95	0.64	Competent	151	3.89	0.76	Competent
Dissemination of Research Results	105	3.87	0.62	Competent	151	3.82	0.73	Competent
The function of Faculty Researchers in SUCs	105	3.80	0.68	Competent	151	3.81	0.73	Competent
Other Relevant Competencies	105	3.91	0.62	Competent	151	3.81	0.72	Competent

Note: 4.21–5.00 Highly Competent; 3.41–4.20 Competent; 2.61–3.40 Moderately Competent; 1.81–2.60 Less Competent; 1.00–1.80 Not Competent

Level of Research Competence of Faculty in SUCs When Grouped According to Faculty Rank

The data in Table 3 shows that when grouped according to Faculty rank, Instructor I – III ($M = 3.87$, $sd = 0.63$), Assistant Professor I – IV ($M = 3.72$, $sd = 0.61$), Associate Professor I – V ($M = 4.01$, $sd = 0.55$), and Professor I – VI ($M = 4.18$, $sd = 0.46$) have "Competent" level of research competence.

In terms of basic skills, Instructor I – III ($M = 4.01$, $sd = 0.63$), Assistant Professor I – IV ($M = 3.87$, $sd = 0.66$), and Associate Professor I – V ($M = 4.11$, $sd = 0.51$) were "Competent," while Professor I – VI ($M = 4.21$, $sd = 0.51$) were found to be "Highly Competent." As to problem-solving and critical thinking skills, Instructor I – III ($M = 3.82$, $sd = 0.76$), Assistant Professor I – IV ($M = 3.81$, $sd = 0.69$), and Associate Professor I – V ($M = 4.11$, $sd = 0.62$) were "Competent," while Professor I – VI ($M = 4.24$, $sd = 0.49$) were found to be "Highly Competent."

Research output is an essential assessment aspect for academic positions. Experiences in conducting research also enhance research competencies (Mallari & Santiago, 2013). Moreover, according to Dapiawen (2017), graduate professors possessed expert knowledge of the components of research papers and were highly able to complete various research activities. Also, the teaching position affects research capability (Wong, 2018).

When the mean per group was assessed, for Instructors, and Assistant Professors, basic skills got the highest mean ($M = 4.01$, $sd = 0.63$; $M = 3.87$, $sd = 0.66$, respectively), while the function of faculty researcher in SUCs got the lowest mean ($M = 3.80$, $sd = 0.74$, $M = 3.60$, $sd = 0.68$). For Associate Professors, basic skills, problem-solving, and critical thinking got the highest mean ($M = 4.11$, $sd = 0.51$, $M = 4.11$, $sd = 0.62$). In contrast, other relevant key competencies got the lowest mean ($M = 3.91$, $sd = 0.67$). For Professors, problem-solving and critical-thinking skills got the highest mean

($M = 4.24$, $sd = 0.49$), while other relevant key competencies got the lowest mean ($M = 4.11$, $sd = 0.52$). The competence of Faculty can be explained by the fact that Faculty in higher education institutions are mandated to do research. The moment they enter the grounds of higher education institutions, they are commissioned to do research, extension, and production as the four functions of all SUCs (Rodriguez et al., 2021). Graduate school instructors possess expert knowledge of the components of research papers and a high ability to complete various research activities (Dapiawen, 2017).

Table 3. Mean Results on the Level of Research Competence of Faculty in SUCs When Grouped According to Faculty Rank

Category	Instructor I – III				Assistant Professor I – IV			
	n	Mean	sd	Description	n	Mean	sd	Description
As a whole	102	3.87	0.63	Competent	73	3.72	0.61	Competent
Basic Skills	102	4.01	0.63	Competent	73	3.87	0.66	Competent
Problem-solving and Critical Thinking Skills	102	3.82	0.76	Competent	73	3.81	0.69	Competent
Dissemination of Research Results	102	3.85	0.69	Competent	73	3.66	0.70	Competent
The function of Faculty Researchers in SUCs	102	3.80	0.74	Competent	73	3.60	0.68	Competent
Other Relevant Competencies	Key102	3.88	0.69	Competent	73	3.69	0.68	Competent

Category	Associate Professor I – V				Professor I – VI			
	n	Mean	sd	Description	n	Mean	sd	Description
As a whole	65	4.01	0.55	Competent	16	4.18	0.46	Competent
Basic Skills	65	4.11	0.51	Competent	16	4.21	0.51	Highly Competent
Problem-solving and Critical Thinking Skills	65	4.11	0.62	Competent	16	4.24	0.49	Highly Competent
Dissemination of Research Results	65	3.96	0.65	Competent	16	4.14	0.50	Competent
The function of Faculty Researchers in SUCs	65	3.96	0.64	Competent	16	4.18	0.64	Competent
Other Relevant Competencies	Key65	3.91	0.67	Competent	16	4.11	0.52	Competent

Note: 4.21–5.00 Highly Competent; 3.41–4.20 Competent; 2.61–3.40 Moderately Competent; 1.81–2.60 Less Competent; 1.00–1.80 Not Competent

The difference in the Level of Research Competence When Grouped According to the Level of Education

Table 4 shows the t-test results for significant differences in the level of research competence when grouped according to the level of education.

Results revealed no significant difference that existed in the level of research competence in terms of Basic Skills ($t = -.427$, $p = 0.670$), Problem-solving, and Critical Thinking Skills ($t = .638$, $p = 0.254$), Dissemination of Research Results ($t = .551$, $p = 0.582$); Function of Faculty Researcher in SUCs ($t = -.160$, $p = 0.873$); and Other Relevant Key Competencies ($t = 1.117$, $p = 0.265$). Thus, the null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in the level of research competence of Faculty in SUCs in terms of fundamental skills; problem-solving, and critical thinking skills; dissemination of research results; function of faculty researchers in SUCs; and other relevant vital competencies when grouped according to the level of education is not rejected.

This means that the level of education is not a significant factor in determining the research competence of Faculty in SUCs. Aspiras (2019) reported that when faculty members are classified according to educational qualifications, there are no significant differences in their research knowledge and skills. During their Master's and undergraduate research courses, Faculty strengthen their research skills (Rodriguez, 2021). Competence develops a new mental formation while mastering certain activities during the research learning process (Prosekov et al., 2020). Roman (2021) reported that competencies about problems and backgrounds, literature, sources and citations, theories and frameworks, research methods, research instrumentations, sampling techniques, research ethics, data analysis procedures, and making interpretations, conclusions, recommendations, and implications are

all in the low extent category while the competency of the HEI faculty in research types is on the average level. Faculty were well-versed in research capability knowledge and technical components (Narag et al., 2016). According to Bueno (2017), Faculty members still need to improve their mastery of research skills evidenced by their outputs and aid graduate students in improving research abilities and professional progress through further research activities. Teachers have average skills in accessing, using, and evaluating information and understanding various sources of information and where to obtain them (Basilio & Bueno, 2019). Tahsildar & Hasani's (2021) inventory on research skills indicated that Faculty perceived to have mid-level research skills with low-level research productivity as evidenced by their research production.

Table 4. t-test Results on the difference in the Level of Research Competence of Faculty in SUCs When Grouped According to Level of Education

Category	n	Education	Mean	t-value	df	Sig.
Basic Skills	105	Master's Degree	3.99	-.427	254	.670
	151	Doctorate Degree/ Level	4.02			
Problem-Solving, and Critical Thinking Skills	105	Master's Degree	3.95	.638	254	.524
	151	Doctorate Degree/ Level	3.89			
Dissemination of Research Results	105	Master's Degree	3.87	.551	254	.582
	151	Doctorate Degree/ Level	3.82			
The function of Faculty Researchers in SUCs	105	Master's Degree	3.80	-.160	584	.873
	151	Doctorate Degree/ Level	3.81			
Other Relevant Key Competencies	105	Master's Degree	3.91	1.117	254	.265
	151	Doctorate Degree/ Level	3.81			

p>.05, not significant

The difference in the Level of Research Competence of Faculty in SUCs When Grouped According to Faculty Rank

Table 5 shows a one-way Analysis of Variance results on the test for significant differences in the level of research competence when grouped according to the number of Faculty ranks. Results revealed no significant difference in the level of research competence regarding basic skills ($f = 2.595$, $p = 0.053$) and other relevant vital competencies ($F = 2.404$, $p = 0.068$). Thus, when grouped according to Faculty rank, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the level of research competence of Faculty in SUCs in terms of basic skills and other relevant vital competencies is not rejected.

This means that Faculty rank is not a significant factor in determining the research competence of Faculty in SUCs in terms of basic skills and other relevant vital competencies. On the other hand, significant differences existed in the level of research competence in terms of problem-solving and critical thinking skills ($f = 4.264$, $p = 0.006$), dissemination of research results ($f = 3.373$, $p = 0.019$), the function of faculty researcher in SUCs ($F = 4.810$, $p = 0.003$). Thus, the null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in the level of research competence of Faculty in SUCs in terms of problem-solving, critical thinking skills; dissemination of research results; function of faculty researchers in SUCs when grouped according to Faculty rank is rejected. This means that Faculty rank is a significant factor in determining the research competence of Faculty in SUCs.

The teaching load in SUCs varies according to Faculty rank. It descends as the Faculty ascends through the ranks and the research load increases. This may contribute to the significant difference in Faculty's competencies level. A heavy teaching load is a key factor preventing a Faculty from conducting research activities. Faculty members need help to devote continuous research time. Approximately one-third of the time spent on teaching is spent on research. This finding is supported by the findings of Zhang (2014), Bland et al. (2005), Ma & Runyon, 2004; and Toews & Yazedjian (2007). According to Aspiras (2019), when faculty members are classified according to academic rank, there are no significant differences in their research knowledge and skills.

Table 5. One-way ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Level of Research Competence of Faculty in SUCs When Grouped According to Faculty Rank

Category		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Basic Skills	Between Groups	2.879	3	.960	2.595	.053
	Within Groups	93.214	252	.370		
	Total	96.094	255			
Problem-solving and Critical Thinking Skills	Between Groups	6.116	3	2.039	4.264	.006*
	Within Groups	120.468	252	.478		
	Total	126.584	255			
Dissemination of Research Results	Between Groups	4.602	3	1.534	3.373	.019*
	Within Groups	114.622	252	.455		
	Total	119.224	255			
The function of Faculty Researchers in SUCs	Between Groups	6.910	3	2.303	4.810	.003*
	Within Groups	120.684	252	.479		
	Total	127.594	255			
Other Relevant Key Competencies	Between Groups	3.296	3	1.099	2.404	.068
	Within Groups	115.144	252	.457		
	Total	118.439	255			

*p<.05, significant

p>.05, not significant

From Table 5-1, Post-hoc comparisons using the Scheffe test indicated that the mean Function of Faculty Researcher scores in SUCs for Faculty rank of Associate Professors and Assistant Professors differed significantly from Assistant Professors (MD=-.363, p= .026; MD=-.578, p=.029, respectively).

Table 5-1. Post Hoc Tests Multiple Comparison; Scheffe Test for Research Competence When Grouped According to Faculty Rank

Dependent Variable	(I) Faculty Rank	(J) Faculty Rank	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig.
Problem-Solving, and Critical Thinking Skills	Instructor I - III	Assistant Professor I - IV	.010	1.000
		Associate Professor 1 - V	-.298	.063
		Professor I - VI	-.422	.164
	Assistant Professor I - IV	Associate Professor 1 - V	-.308	.080
		Professor I - VI	-.432	.166
		Associate Professor 1 - V	-.124	.938
Dissemination of Research Results	Instructor I - III	Assistant Professor I - IV	.188	.349
		Associate Professor 1 - V	-.106	.806
		Professor I - VI	-.287	.477
	Assistant Professor I - IV	Associate Professor 1 - V	-.294	.091
		Professor I - VI	-.474	.093
		Associate Professor 1 - V	.181	.820
The function of Faculty Researchers in SUCs	Instructor I - III	Assistant Professor I - IV	.199	.321
		Associate Professor 1 - V	-.164	.528
		Professor I - VI	-.379	.249
	Assistant Professor I - IV	Associate Professor 1 - V	-.363*	.026
		Professor I - VI	-.578*	.029
		Associate Professor 1 - V	-.215	.744

CONCLUSION

This study tried to determine the research competence of Faculty in State Universities and Colleges in Iloilo. Generally, the Faculty respondents are "Competent" in research in terms of basic skills; problem-solving and critical thinking skills; dissemination of research results; function of faculty researcher in SUCs; and other relevant key competencies. The Faculty still need to learn how to do research and time management. They have yet to establish a timeline for when to finish the research.

No significant difference existed in the level of research competence of Faculty in SUCs in all categories when grouped according to the level of education. This means that level of education is not a significant factor in determining the level of research competence of Faculty in SUCs.

The level of research competence regarding Basic Skills and Other Relevant Key Competencies is the same when grouped according to Faculty rank. This means that Faculty rank is not a significant factor in determining the research competence of Faculty in SUCs in terms of Basic Skills and Other Relevant Key Competencies.

Research competency was significantly different regarding Problem-Solving and Critical Thinking Skills, Dissemination of Research Results, and Faculty Researcher Function in SUCs. In SUCs, Faculty rank is crucial in determining faculty research capability. Professors have mastered the fundamental abilities to research as they rise in the ranks.

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